

significantly less than to urea at 60 and 120 kg N/ha. Poultry manure at 60, 120, and 180 kg N/ha produced rice grain yield equivalent to that by 37, 96, and 168 kg urea N/ha, respectively. On the basis of N uptake, poultry manure N was 80% as efficient as urea N at all rates of application.

Urea and manure differ in increasing

rice grain yield at 60 kg N/ha, perhaps because at low application rates, sufficient manure N might not be mineralized for critical growth stages of rice. No significant differences in uptake of P and K by rice were observed between urea and poultry manure.

A residual effect of poultry manure N was shown by wheat grown after rice

only at the highest rate of application (see table). The residual effect of the manure in supplying P to wheat was conspicuous, both through Olsen's available P and a significant response of wheat to 26 kg P/ha in plots where poultry manure had been applied to rice at 0, 60, and 120 kg N/ha. □

Nitrogen-fixing potential of blue-green algae (BGA) from Kerala ricefields

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We studied the effect of P and Mo on N fixation by a mixture of BGA in 1-liter beakers containing 200 g each of air-dried soil from Trichur district (pH 4.56, CEC 21 meq/100 g, C 3.2196, N 31%) brought to neutrality by adding calcium carbonate at 700 kg/ha. Two levels of Mo (0.2 and 0.4 ppm) and 2 levels of P (4 and 8 kg/ha) were used, in 9 treatments replicated 3 times.

BGA crust at 10 kg/ha was inoculated. The beakers were kept in the open for 3 wk with water level

Effect of Mo and P on N fixation^a by BGA in Kerala ricefields, India.

	N fixation ^b (kg/ha)			Mean
	No Mo (control)	0.2 ppm Mo	0.4 ppm Mo	
No P (control)	6.3	6.3	12.5	8.4
4 kg P/ha	12.5	15.7	9.4	12.5
8 kg P/ha	9.4	12.5	18.8	13.6
Mean	9.4	11.5	13.6	

^aTotal N after 3 wk - initial N. ^bCD (0.05) for comparison of Mo and P = 3.16.

Confidence limit for means = ± 2.109

CD (0.05) for comparison of combinations = 5.48

Confidence limit for cells = ± 3.653

maintained at 5-10 cm above soil level. Then the soil was allowed to dry and the BGA crust was incorporated. Total N was determined by the microKjeldahl method.

Both Mo and P had favorable influence on N fixation. The combination treatment 8 kg P/ha and

0.4 ppm Mo fixed the largest amount of N (see table). At 8 kg P/ha, each additional Mo level improved N fixation by BGA. On average, addition of 0.4 ppm Mo increased N fixation by 44% over the control; addition of 8 kg P/ha increased N fixation by 62% over the control. □

Rice-based Cropping Systems

Effect of an interim summer crop in a rice - wheat rotation

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During the summer (May-Jun) in the Punjab, a shortduration crop is grown between the dry and wet season main crops. This crop could be a cereal fodder, a pulse, or a green manure.

Green manuring is gaining importance with increasing costs of

fertilizers and threats of pollution. In rice, green manuring with sesbania has been successfully used to supplement fertilizer N. On the other hand, growing a cereal fodder might deplete available nutrients and adversely affect rice yield. We conducted a field experiment 1984-85 to study the effect of summer maize *Zea mays* fodder, mungbean *Phaseolus aureus* pulse, cowpea *Vigna sinensis*, sunn hemp *Crotalaria juncea*, and sesbania *Sesbania aculeata* green manure (GM) crops on the following rice crop.

Soil was a sandy loam (Typic Ustochrept), alkaline (pH 8.5), with 0.40% organic C, 7.5 kg available P/ha, and 81 kg available K/ha.

Crops were planted the first week of May. Maize was fertilized with 120 kg N/ha applied in 2 splits and harvested for fodder at 2 mo. Mature mungbean pods were picked. Mungbean residue and the 3 green manure crops were incorporated 1 d before transplanting rice. N was applied to rice at 60, 120, and 180 kg/ha in 3 equal splits (1/3 at transplanting, 1/3 3 wk and 1/3 6 wk